

Graded Hydrolysis of Cashew Nut Shell Polysaccharide: II. Structures of Trisaccharide and Tetrasaccharides*

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The structures of one trisaccharide and two tetrasaccharides obtained by graded hydrolysis of water soluble cashew nut shell polysaccharide have been elucidated from periodate oxidation, Smith degradation and methylation experiments. Trisaccharide (I) and tetrasaccharide (II) are straight chain oligosaccharides comprised of galactose moieties only. In (I) the glycosidic linkages are 1→3 while in (II) both 1→3 and 1→6 linkages are present. The remaining tetrasaccharide (III) composed of galactose units only is branched chain in character, carrying both 1→3 and 1→6 linkages. The isolation of (III) as a graded hydrolysis product of natural polysaccharide has not been reported so far.

An earlier study¹ has revealed that the neutral oligosaccharide mixture obtained after graded hydrolysis of water soluble cashew nut shell polysaccharide is composed of one di-, one tri-, and two tetrasaccharides. The characterisation of the disaccharide as 3-*o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl-D-galactose has already been reported. The present communication deals with the structure of one tri- and two tetrasaccharides which has remained unidentified earlier.

The trisaccharide, m.p. 139°–41°, on complete acid hydrolysis and chromatographic examination gave galactose as the only monosaccharide. The linkages between the galactose moieties have been ascertained from the results of periodate oxidation and Smith degradation and finally from methylation experiments.

The trisaccharide was converted into its methyl glycoside derivative by refluxing with methanolic hydrogen chloride. This, upon oxidation with sodium metaperiodate produced one mole of formic acid with concomitant consumption of two moles of the reagent. Further, the periodate oxidised product on Smith degradation, gave rise to glycolaldehyde, glycerol and galactose which were identified by paper chromatography. After complete methylation and hydrolysis, the trisaccharide furnished 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (1 mole) and 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (2 moles) which were identified through their migration rates and the m.p.s. of their crystalline anilide derivatives. The above findings as well as the specific rotation of the compound indicate that the trisaccharide may be designated as *o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1→3)-*o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1→3)-D-galactopyranose. May and Weinland² reported the m.p. of the compound as 115°–20° which is somewhat lower than the present value.

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The tetrasaccharide, m.p. 128°–30°, is composed of D-galactoses only as could be observed from its hydrolytic behaviour under acidic conditions. Methyl glycoside derivative of the compound consumes four moles of periodate for complete oxidation thereby liberating two moles of formic acid. Periodate oxidised product after Smith degradation indicated the presence of glycolaldehyde, glycerol and galactose. Fully methylated tetrasaccharide on acid hydrolysis produced 2,3,4,6-tetra-, 2,4,6-tri-, and 2,3,4-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactose in the ratio of 1 : 2 : 1. Based upon these observations, tetrasaccharide (II) has been assigned *o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)-*o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)-*o*- β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 6)-D-galactopyranose structure. A tetrasaccharide of similar structure was isolated earlier by Haq and Adams as a hydrolysis product of Tamarack arabinogalactan³.

The structural elucidation of the remaining tetrasaccharide, m.p. 120°–22°, shows it to be a new oligosaccharide since its occurrence as a partial hydrolysis product of a plant polysaccharide has not been reported so far. Acid hydrolysis of the compound showed that it was built up of galactose units only. Methyl glycoside derivative of the compound on being oxidised with periodate, consumed four moles of the reagent with simultaneous liberation of two moles of formic acid. Completely methylated tetrasaccharide after acid hydrolysis gave rise to 2,3,4,6-tetra-(2 moles), 2,4,6-tri-(1 mole), and 2,4-di-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (1 mole). The isolation of two moles of tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose and also the nature of di-*o*-methyl-D-galactose indicate that the tetrasaccharide possesses a branched chain structure in which one galactose unit is linked at 3 and 6 positions with two other galactose units. Accordingly the following tentative structure (III) has been advanced for the tetrasaccharide which is also in agreement with periodate oxidation results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out at 40°–50° under diminished pressure. All specific rotations are equilibrium values and m.ps. are uncorrected. Paper chromatographic analysis were carried out by descending method on Whatman No. 1 filter paper sheets with the non-aqueous phases of the following solvents (v/v) : (S₁), butanol-pyridine-water-benzene (5 : 3 : 3 : 1); (S₂), butanol-ethanol-water (4 : 1 : 5); (S₃), butanone-water-ammonia (200 : 17 : 2); (S₄), ethyl acetate-butanone-water-ammonia (80 : 20 : 8 : 1). Spray

reagents used were (R_1) sodium metaperiodate—benzidine- B^4 , (R_2) *p*-anisidine hydrochloride⁵. R_g values of the methylated sugars refer to the rates of movement relative to 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-*D*-glucose.

Characterisation of the galactotriose (I) : (I), $[\alpha]_D^{33} + 31.8^\circ$ (C, 1.05 g in water), m.p. $139^\circ - 41^\circ$, as isolated earlier from the graded hydrolysis of cashew nut shell polysaccharide¹ was chromatographically pure. Acid hydrolysis of the compound produced exclusively galactose.

(i) *Periodate oxidation* : (I), (0.0702 g) was converted into its methylglycoside derivative by refluxing with methanolic hydrogen chloride for 4 hr. An aqueous solution of the methyl glycoside (0.0578 g, 20 ml) was treated with sodium metaperiodate solution (0.5082 g, 25 ml) and kept in dark for 7 days at room temperature. The volume of the solution was then made upto 100 ml and aliquots (5 ml each) were taken out and titrated for periodate uptake⁶ and formic acid liberation^{7,8}. Formic acid produced and periodate consumed (mean value) at the final stage were found to be 1.25 and 2.16 moles respectively per mole of the methylglycoside derivative of the trisaccharide.

(ii) *Smith degradation⁹ of the galactotriose* : The remaining periodate oxidised solution was treated with ethylene glycol (3 ml) to decompose excess of periodate. Inorganic ions were removed by treatment with freshly regenerated cation (Duolite C-25) and anion exchange (Amberlite-411) resins. Deionised solution was concentrated (10 ml) and to it, sodium borohydride (0.25 g) was added in small quantities at a time with constant stirring for 24 hr. After removal of excess of borohydride by addition of aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, 10 ml) the resultant solution was evaporated to dryness. The residue was then distilled several times with absolute methanol (5 ml each) to remove borate ions as methyl borate. The borate free reduction product was then hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (1*N*, 10 ml) for 10 hr. The hydrolysate, after being worked up in usual manner, was concentrated to a thin syrup. This, upon paper chromatographic examination (Solvent S_1 , spray reagent R_1) furnished three spots (white on a blue back ground) corresponding to galactose glycerol and glycolaldehyde.

(iii) *Methylation¹⁰ of the galactotriose* : The compound (0.1286 g) was dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (20 ml) by stirring and warming to 45° . Sodium hydride (0.5148 g) was then added in portions over 2.5 hr. Stirring was continued for further 4 hr at $50-60^\circ$ till the evolution of hydrogen had ceased. To the solution cooled to room temperature, was added methyl iodide (5 ml) during 75 min. Stirring was continued overnight (14 hr). Two further additions of sodium hydride (0.3718 g) and methyl iodide (5 ml) were made on successive days. Chloroform (150 ml) was then added to extract the reaction mixture, a drop of which gave neutral test when added to water and spotted on *pH* paper. The chloroform solution was filtered free of sodium iodide and extracted thoroughly with water (1 l.) to remove dimethyl sulphoxide. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the residue was extracted thoroughly with chloroform. The combined chloroform extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a syrup (0.1018 g). This was subjected to Purdie's methylation¹¹ by dissolving it in methyl iodide (6 ml) and adding to it silver oxide (0.8 g) in small quantities during 8 hr with gentle refluxing and

stirring. The mixture was filtered and the residue was extracted exhaustively with chloroform. The combined filtrate was concentrated to syrup (yield 0.094 g) (Found : OMe, 50.88; $C_{29}H_{54}O_{18}$ requires -OMe, 51.8%). I.R. spectrum of the methylated product showed complete absence of absorption band in the -OH region.

(iv) *Hydrolysis*¹² of the methylated compound : Syrup (0.08 g) was mixed with 72% sulphuric acid (w/w, 0.5 ml) and kept for one hour at room temperature when the solution turned dark brown. The concentration of the acid was then reduced to 12% (w/w) by dilution with calculated amount of water (3 ml.). At this stage the colour changed to green. The solution was heated on steam bath for 4 hr. It was neutralised ($BaCO_3$) and concentrated to a thin syrup. This was made alkaline (pH 8.0), saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor for 30 hr., to obtain the methylated neutral sugar mixture (yield 0.0264 g).

The syrup after resolution on filter paper sheets (solvent S_2 and spray reagent R_2) gave two fractions :

(a) 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (7 mg, R_g 0.9) : On being heated with aniline (6 mg) in ethanol (2 ml) for 3 hr it gave the anilide which was crystallised from ethanol. After recrystallization from the same solvent it had m.p. and m.m.p. 189°–90°.

(b) 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (15 mg, R_g 0.68) : It furnished a crystalline anilide derivative m.p. and m.m.p. 175°–77°.

Galactotetraose (II) : (II), m.p. 128°–30°, was chromatographically homogeneous. Acid hydrolysis of compound furnished a single spot of galactose only. An aqueous solution of methylglycoside derivative (0.0236 g) was treated with sodium metaperiodate (0.2092 g) at room temperature for 100 hr. After completion of the reaction, periodate consumed and formic acid liberated were 4.14 and 2.39 moles respectively. Smith degradation⁹ of the remaining periodate oxidised solution was carried out as described earlier. After working up in the usual manner, spots corresponding to galactose and glycerol were detected on the paper chromatogram.

Complete methylation of tetrasaccharide (0.2250 g) was carried out according to the method of Anderson and Cree¹⁰ followed by Purdie's methylation as in previous experiment (Yield 0.071 g. Found : OMe, 49.90; $C_{38}H_{70}O_{21}$ requires—OMe, 50.35%). I.R. spectrum of methylated product showed complete absence of -OH band. Hydrolysis of the methylated product was done in the same manner as described before. Paper chromatography of the resultant methylated sugars (solvent S_3 , spray reagent R_2) showed two spots. The faster one (R_g 0.86) corresponded to 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose while the slower one (R_g 0.42) which is of elongated shape, indicated the presence of a mixture of 2,3,4-tri- and 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactose.

The mixture after resolution on filter paper sheets (solvent S_3) yielded (a) 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (9 mg), characterised through its crystalline anilide derivative, m.p. 190°–92°, and (b) a mixture of 2,3,4- and 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactoses (30 mg). Rechromatography of the mixture was carried out five times on the same paper sheet until the separation of two compounds were distinct. However $\frac{1}{2}$ " of the paper in the middle of

the band of the sugars was discarded and top portion of the band was extracted with water to give a sugar (9 mg) which yielded 2,3,4-tri-*o*-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine derivative, m.p. and m.m.p. 165°. The lower portion of paper gave a sugar (16 mg) which furnished a crystalline 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-N-phenyl-D-galactosylamine derivative, m.p. and m.m.p. 176°–78°.

Galactotetraose (III): (III), $[\alpha]_D^{33} + 6.5^\circ$ (C, 0.92 g in water), m.p. 120°–22°, was chromatographically pure. Acid hydrolysis of the compound furnished galactose only. Methyl glycoside derivative of the tetrasaccharide (0.0256 g) on oxidation with periodate (0.2290 g) consumed 4.31 moles of periodate with simultaneous liberation of 2.12 moles of formic acid.

The tetrasaccharide was fully methylated by adopting the procedure of Perlia and Bishop¹³. The compound (0.047 g) was shaken with methyl iodide (9 ml), freshly distilled dimethyl formamide (10 ml) and silver oxide (3 g) at room temperature in the dark for 18 hr. The mixture was filtered and the residue was washed with chloroform. The combined filtrate and washings were dried and evaporated to dryness under vacuum at room temperature and finally dried at 65°–70°. I.R. spectrum of the methylated product showed complete absence of -OH band. Acid hydrolysis of the methylated product was carried out in the usual way. The reaction product, after working up, yielded a mixture of methylated sugars (yield, 0.038 g) which on paper chromatographic examination produced three distinct spots R_f 0.82, 0.68 and 0.42 in solvent S_2 and R_f 0.73, 0.38 and 0.13 in solvent S_3 . Resolution of this mixture on Whatman No. 1 filter paper sheets yielded (a) 2,3,4,6-tetra-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (19 mg), anilide, m.p. 189°–90°, (b) 2,4,6-tri-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (8 mg), anilide, m.p. 175°–77°, and (c) 2,4-di-*o*-methyl-D-galactose (6 mg), monohydrate crystallized from acetone, m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample 97°–98°.

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